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Project Information

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Project Summary

European musical heritage is a dynamic historical flow of experiences, leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to capture, connect, access, interpret, and valorise. Computing technologies have the potential to shed a light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hence revealing facts and experiences from hidden voices of the past. Polifonia makes this happen by building novel ways of inspecting, representing, and interacting with digital content. Memory institutions, scholars, and citizens will be able to navigate, explore, and discover multiple perspectives and stories about European Musical Heritage.

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts - or music objects - (tunes, scores, melodies, notations, etc.) along with relevant knowledge about them such as: their links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.), their cultural and historical contexts, opinions and stories told by people having diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc), and facts expressed in different styles and disciplines (memoire, reportage, news, biographies, reviews), different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German), and across centuries.

The overall goal of the project is to realise an ecosystem of computational methods and tools supporting discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge on the Web. An equally important objective is to demonstrate that these tools improve the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities (SSH) methodologies. Hence their development is guided by, and continuously intertwined with, experiments and validations performed in real-world settings, identified by musical heritage stakeholders (both belonging to the Consortium and external supporters) such as cultural institutes and collection owners, historians of music, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, linguists, etc.

Executive Summary

In this deliverable, we report work on finding and exploiting local patterns in musical score data. Local patterns or motifs have long been seen as key to understanding musical relationships between pieces of music within and between corpora, in musicology and especially in the sub-field of ethnomusicology (these ideas are explained more fully, with citations, in the following chapters).

We represent local patterns as n -grams of pitch values. We investigate many variants of this basic idea, using them to extract important patterns from a large corpus.

We investigate how these patterns can be used to detect relationships among tunes, leading to a central application of our pattern work: a tune family detection task. The concept of tune families, again, is a cornerstone of ethnomusicology research. A tune family is a set of tunes which are musically similar, and are believed to have developed from common origins through the processes of variation characteristic of an oral tradition. Tune family detection can be seen as a variant of a cover-song detection task, since the fundamental question in both cases is how to identify that two pieces, among many, share sufficient musical similarity to judge that one may have occurred as a variant of another: a cover song, or a tune variant in an oral tradition. Both types of task are well-known in the music information retrieval literature. To enable the tune family detection task, we have labelled a subset of the dataset with tune family ground truth labels.

At this point, we report on some examples of important patterns and the tune relationships they help us to uncover.

Moving on, we then process the patterns extracted above into linked open data, i.e. a knowledge graph. We design and present an ontology to represent musical patterns. We discuss the software pipeline used to process the raw pattern data to linked open data. We demonstrate examples of using this linked open data via SPARQL queries and their results.

For the applications and experiments reported in this deliverable, we focus on *The Session*, a large online crowd-sourced corpus of 40,152 tunes from the broad Irish folk tradition. We extract 200,000 important patterns and create a knowledge graph of 45 million statements.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Deliverable details

Deliverable D3.4 is titled: *Analysis of found musical patterns to identify their relationships*. To quote from the Polifonia Grant Agreement: “Relying on results of previous deliverables in this workpackage, this deliverables reports on experiment to extract relationships between identified patterns in repositories of structured music information.” Central sub-tasks include identifying frequent and significant patterns in music segments, and formally expressing these patterns and relations with other concepts including other patterns.

It is linked to Task 1 of WP3: *Pattern extraction* and Task 2 of WP3: *pattern recognition and definition in monodic and polyphonic music*. The leader for both Tasks is NUIG and the participants are: UNIBO, OU, KCL, CNRS, CNAM, KNAW. D3.4 is due in month 26 (extended from month 24 by agreement). This deliverable follows on from D3.2 *Analysis of music repositories to identify musical patterns*, delivered in month 12. Related deliverables in WP3, D3.5 and D3.6, are also planned at Months 30 and 36. Thus this document D3.4 reports on substantial progress, but not the final results of the WP.

D3.4 is organised into this introduction, followed by two core chapters as follows.

Finding important patterns Local patterns are a fascinating approach to musicology. Here, an n -gram approach is used to characterise patterns, leading to a large pattern corpus. Frequent common patterns are identified as significant. This allows us to identify related melodies and explore tune families in the corpus. The approach has been validated and compared to alternatives thanks to new annotation of ground truth on tune families. Examples and results are described.

Representing and exploring patterns in linked open data We have processed the patterns to produce Linked Open Data in the form of Knowledge Graphs in RDF format. These are available on the web for querying. This piece of work, including the knowledge engineering, SPARQL endpoint, and a data story based on the MELODY software, is reported fully under WP1/WP2. However, we have also developed SPARQL queries allowing the user to query the data for tune similarity, based on the methods for extracting significant patterns, mentioned above. This allows users (both musicologists and members of the public) to explore corpora by searching for tunes containing similar patterns. This work including examples of pattern queries is reported here as part of WP3.

Finally, we have conclusions, followed by a statement on FAIR principles.

2 Patterns in Irish Traditional music

2.1 Background

2.1.1 Context and summary

Since the 19th century, studies of Western folk music have sought to identify common melodic and structural elements between and within tunes [1]. The larger, related task of tracing the movements and ancestry of tunes which exist in similar-but-different versions within traditions and across multiple traditions is also a long-standing and important concern in the ethnomusicology of Western folk music [2]. This concept was formalized by American collector and ethnomusicologist Samuel Bayard in 1950 in what he termed ‘tune families’ [3]. Tune family detection has been the focus of much work but has not yet been solved in a satisfying or definitive study.

From the mid-1960s onwards, the field of computational musicology came into being. Applying techniques and concepts from computational musicology to ethnomusicological questions, the subfield of computational ethnomusicology emerged in the latter 20th century. In the last two decades, with the widespread availability of powerful computing resources, computational ethnomusicology studies of folk corpora have proliferated widely [2, 4].

The field of Music Information Retrieval (MIR) overlaps and feeds into computational ethnomusicology. It entails applying and tailoring Information Retrieval techniques to music-specific applications [5] such as query-by-humming; cover-song and genre detection, and song recommendation. The application reported here falls broadly into the category of a cover-song detection task. State-of-the-art work in this area of musical similarity detection most frequently uses local and/or global alignment algorithms [6, 7]; recent work in the field has expanded into use of Machine Learning tools such as embedding and LSTMs [6, 8, 9].

Informed by an extensive review of the fields introduced above (reported in Deliverable 3.1), we have created tools to search a corpus for tunes similar to a query tune. Multiple similarity metrics have been developed, all of which are based on local melodic pattern similarity within feature sequence data extracted from an input corpus via the FoNN toolkit [10]. Our current methodology involves detection of melodic similarity by finding frequent and/or similar local patterns in diatonic scale degree sequences extracted from scores in ABC notation. These tools have been developed on a corpus of Irish folk melodies but can be applied to any monophonic symbolic music input data in either ABC notation or MIDI format.

Note: Diatonic scale degrees are diatonic pitches normalized to a single octave, represented by an integer value between 1 and 7. The tools under development investigate local melodic patterns at two levels of granularity: accent-level and note-level, as illustrated in Figure 2.1.

For the work reported in this deliverable we used *The Session*, a large online crowd-sourced

Tune Structure: Lord McDonald's (reel) [excerpt]

A part (bars 1-8)	
<p style="text-align: center;">Phrase 1 / Incipit</p>	
B part (bars 9-16)	
<p style="text-align: center;">Phrase 3</p>	

Figure 2.2: Illustration of structural elements in *Lord McDonald's (reel)* from the *CRÉ* corpus [21]. The incipit and first part-ending cadence are highlighted in red, as are the accented notes.

2.2 Pre-processing

2.2.1 Corpus selection

The website thesession.org (*The Session*) was created by musician and web developer Jeremy Keith in 2001 [22]. It consists of a discussion forum and a crowd-sourced tune repository focused on Irish traditional music. Over its two decades of existence, *The Session* has come to be one of the most important online resources for the global Irish traditional music community, with its tune corpus providing a widely-used reference for students, teachers, performers and researchers. *The Session* corpus holds over 40,000 monophonic traditional tune melodies in ABC and MIDI formats. It is open, crowd-sourced, and although based on the Irish tradition, it also contains material from other folk traditions and contemporary folk tunes. A weekly dump of the website's content, including the full tune corpus in ABC format, is available for download via [Github](https://github.com). A download of the corpus on December 13th 2021 provided the basis for our working version of the corpus [23].

2.2.2 Ground-truth annotation

Initial work on tune similarity within the *CRÉ* corpus (reported in Deliverable 3.1) proved difficult to verify due to the absence of ground truth data. Moving to *The Session* allowed use of its in-built tune title and variant identifiers as proxies for ground truth annotation. Within *The Session* it is common for a single tune to be present in many related but subtly-different melodic variants. All variants of a given tune share a common title but are differentiated by variant id numbers, as illustrated below in Figure 2.3. This information enables quantitative evaluation of tune similarity search results: for a given candidate tune, the number of related variants returned and their relative rankings can be quantified. This tune variant annotation is a valuable resource as results validation is a persistent problem in work on traditional tune similarity field. As such, *The Session* corpus is particularly well-suited for development of melodic similarity tools.

As outlined above, the concept of tune families is central in the ethnomusicology of Irish and related Western folk music traditions. Manual and computational identification of tune families within and between corpora and traditions is a long standing research question which has not yet been fully resolved. Tune family identification is the ultimate focus of the work presented here, and, although *The Session's* built-in variant similarity annotation is of use for tune similarity searching, it is not in itself directly helpful for this tune family identification. However, when augmented with information from the ethnomusicological literature, it was possible to use *The Session's* variant annotation to generate quantitative tune family ground truth annotation.

Working from the literature on tune families in the Irish tradition, 10 academically-identified tune families were selected. For each family, the titles of its constituent melodies were manually collated from a variety of historical and contemporary ethnomusicological sources [24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32]. *The Session* was searched for occurrences of tune variants associated with each of the 10 tune families. As the corpus is crowd-sourced, the accuracy of its content not always reliable. Accordingly, each variant within the 10 tune families was manually checked by a domain expert to ensure the accuracy of its designation as a tune family member. As a result of this manual inspection pass, 12 of the 327 tune variants found by this search within *The Session* were discarded.

For each tune family, the above process resulted in a list of academically-identified, manually-verified 'family member' tunes occurring in the corpus. A total of 315 tune variants were identified across the 10 families, and this annotation was used as ground truth in the tune similarity search experiments described below.

2.2.3 Corpus ingest

An ABC dump of *The Session* corpus was processed via the latest iteration of FoNN's data ingest tool, which uses the *music21* Python library [33] to extract primary feature sequence data from ABC notation (or MIDI) inputs. The first processing step converts each note in a given score to pitch, onset, duration, and velocity values, per Figure 2.4 below. From these values additional secondary feature sequences are calculated. In total, each note is represented by 15 melodic and rhythmic features including interval, key-invariant pitch, pitch class, scale degree, inter-onset

	Hob or Nob	O'Sullivan's March	Road to Lisdoonvarna	Lord McDonald's	Johnny Cope
0	AnSeanduneDite1029	IWontBeANun16754	KerryCowThe15726	BritchesFullOfStitchesThe1075	BankOfTurfThe1128
1	AnSeanduneDite14252	IWontBeANun29647	KerryCowThe21437	BritchesFullOfStitchesThe14304	BankOfTurfThe14388
2	AnSeanduneDite25163	IWontBeANun3822	KerryCowThe2379	BritchesFullOfStitchesThe22684	DrunkenSailorsThe13516
3	AnSeanduneDite27315	OSullivansMarch15569	KerryCowThe34622	BritchesFullOfStitchesThe24427	DrunkenSailorsThe13517
4	AnSeanduneDite27316	OSullivansMarch15570	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe12965	BritchesFullOfStitchesThe28608	DrunkenSailorsThe20770
5	AnSeanduneDite27842	OSullivansMarch15571	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe12966	BritchesFullOfStitchesThe30507	DrunkenSailorsThe24821
6	AnSeanduneDite29508	OSullivansMarch15572	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe12967	BritchesFullOfStitchesThe31614	DrunkenSailorsThe30531
7	AnSeanduneDite39472	OSullivansMarch15573	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe12968	BritchesFullOfStitchesThe32753	DrunkenSailorsThe32089
8	CampbellsAreComingThe29348	OSullivansMarch15574	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe12969	LordMcDonalds13430	DrunkenSailorsThe553
9	CampbellsAreComingThe29515	OSullivansMarch2204	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe12970	LordMcDonalds13431	GrovesThe16832
10	CampbellsAreComingThe31916	OSullivansMarch22666	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe12971	LordMcDonalds13432	GrovesThe21469
11	CampbellsAreComingThe32702	OSullivansMarch22667	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe12972	LordMcDonalds13433	GrovesThe35948
12	MissMcLeods12552	OSullivansMarch22668	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe21776	LordMcDonalds23658	GrovesThe38611
13	MissMcLeods12553	OSullivansMarch25092	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe249	LordMcDonalds27913	HeyJohnnyCope10105
14	MissMcLeods12554	OSullivansMarch27381	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe250	LordMcDonalds30618	HeyJohnnyCope20222
15	MissMcLeods12556	OSullivansMarch32109	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe25089	LordMcDonalds38959	HeyJohnnyCope20223
16	MissMcLeods12557	OSullivansMarch32487	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe27843	LordMcDonalds507	HeyJohnnyCope20224
17	MissMcLeods12558	OSullivansMarch34265	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe32320	NoonLassiesThe1729	JohnnyCope15700
18	MissMcLeods12559	OSullivansMarch35995	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe36691	NoonLassiesThe23964	JohnnyCope15701
19	MissMcLeods12560	OSullivansMarch40433	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe36697	NoonLassiesThe30965	JohnnyCope15702
20	MissMcLeods21434	OSullivansMarch42104	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe41930	NoonLassiesThe33566	JohnnyCope17346

Figure 2.3: Excerpt from tune family annotation data table: each column lists variants present in *The Session* corpus for the named tune family.

interval (i.e.: duration), bar number, and simple melodic contour represented in Parsons code [34]. All pitch-based features are represented in both chromatic and diatonic formats.

In the initial feature sequence data, each note in the score is represented as a row of feature values. An additional processing step creates a ‘duration-weighted’ version of this data with a re-scaled index, a widely-used technique in the literature on melodic similarity detection [35, 36]. In duration-weighted format each row holds feature values for a single eighth-note temporal increment rather than for a note. See Figures 2.4 and 2.5 for illustrations of the feature sequence conversion process and sample output data.

In a final processing step, the feature sequence data is filtered to create a higher-level representation of the tune, retaining data for rhythmically-accented notes only. This ‘accent-level’ data is used as a parallel experimental input alongside the duration-weighted note-level data. Our use of accent-level input data is based on the ethnomusicological writings on Irish traditional music cited above [14, 15, 16, 17]. It also follows the example of previous multi-level computational similarity work carried out on folk corpora in [18, 37, 38].

Note: As can be seen in Figures 2.4 and 2.5, for all tunes in the corpus, any anacruses or ‘pick-up’ bars prepended before the first full bar of the melody are removed during conversion to feature sequence format.

The current release of the FoNN corpus processing software is available on Github at

https://github.com/polifonia-project/folk_ngram_analysis/releases and was reported in Deliverables 3.2 and 3.3. Its next release will be reported and made available in Deliverable 3.5.

Figure 2.4: Excerpt from *LordMcDonalds507* showing score and primary feature sequence values for each note, with accented notes highlighted in red.

eighth_note	midi_note_num	diatonic_note_num	chromatic_pitch_class	bar_count	chromatic_scale_degree	diatonic_scale_degree	chromatic_interval	diatonic_interval	parsons_code
0	62	30	2	1	7	5	0	0	0
1	67	33	7	1	0	1	5	3	1
2	71	35	11	1	4	3	4	2	1
3	67	33	7	1	0	1	-4	-2	-1
4	74	37	2	1	7	5	7	4	1
5	67	33	7	1	0	1	-7	-4	-1
6	71	35	11	1	4	3	4	2	1
7	67	33	7	1	0	1	-4	-2	-1
8	72	36	0	2	5	4	5	3	1
9	71	35	11	2	4	3	-1	-1	-1
10	71	35	11	2	4	3	-1	-1	-1
11	72	36	0	2	5	4	1	1	1
12	69	34	9	2	2	2	-3	-2	-1
13	67	33	7	2	0	1	-2	-1	-1
14	64	31	4	2	9	6	-3	-2	-1

Figure 2.5: Selected columns from the duration-weighted feature sequence data table for *LordMcDonalds507*, corresponding to the score excerpt displayed in Figure 2.4. Accent-level values are highlighted in red.

2.2.4 Extraction of frequent and structural patterns

For all tunes in the corpus, local n -gram patterns were extracted from the diatonic scale degree sequences at accent- and (duration-weighted) note-level using FoNN’s pattern extraction tool. This tool has been refactored from a previous version reported in Deliverable 3.1, moving to a vectorized implementation utilizing scikit-learn’s feature extraction tools and SciPy’s sparse matrix types, which allowed high-performance local processing of large-scale corpora in minutes.

At both accent- and note-level, n -gram patterns for $3 \leq n \leq 9$ which occur one or more times in the corpus were extracted and stored in an array. This range of n values allowed targeting of patterns of approximately 4 bars of musical content at accent-level, corresponding to the length of a typical phrase in most Western folk tunes, as illustrated above in 2.2. This range of n -values also follows that used in [2]. At note-level it extracts patterns of at least 1 bar at note-level, for all commonly-occurring time signatures in Western folk tunes. TF-IDF values [39, 40] for each pattern occurrence in each tune were calculated and stored in sparse matrices per the excerpt in Figure 2.6 below. These corpus-level tables of pattern occurrences provide the input data for the *motif* and *TFIDF* similarity metrics discussed below. These data are collectively referred to as the “pattern corpus”.

In addition, structurally-important sub-sequences representing the incipit and first part-ending cadence were extracted from the diatonic scale degree sequences, combined, and stored in a corpus-level table per Figure 2.7. This table provides the input data for the *incipit and cadence* similarity metrics discussed below.

patterns	72ndHighlandersFarewellToAberdeenThe28289	AnneFraserMacKenzie21588	AndyDeJarlis13997	BagOfSpudsThe13569
[1 1 1]	0	0.014	0.086	0
[1 1 1 1]	0	0	0.042	0
[1 1 1 1 1]	0	0	0.025	0
[1 1 1 1 1 1]	0	0	0	0
[1 1 1 1 1 1 1]	0	0	0	0
[1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1]	0	0	0	0
[1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 3]	0	0	0	0
[1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 5]	0	0	0	0

Figure 2.6: Excerpt from sample "pattern corpus" TF-IDF data table: the index lists all patterns which occur at least once in the corpus; non-zero column values denote an occurrence of a pattern in a given tune. The magnitude of non-zero TF-IDF values corresponds to a pattern’s frequency within a tune weighted by its frequency across the corpus.

	72ndHighlandersFarewellToAberdeenThe28289	AnneFraserMacKenzie21588	AndyDeJarlis13997	BagOfSpudsThe13569
0	7	5	5	5
1	6	1	1	2
2	5	1	3	2
3	1	1	5	5
4	1	7	1	7
5	1	1	3	5
6	1	2	5	2
7	2	1	1	5
8	2	1	3	5
9	3	1	5	6
10	4	2	6	7

Figure 2.7: Excerpt from incipit and cadences table: each column contains diatonic scale degree sequences representing the incipit and cadence of an individual tune.

2.3 Methodology

2.3.1 Overview

Three approaches to melodic similarity have been developed: *motif* (motif-based alignment of local patterns), *incipit and cadence* (global alignment of incipits / incipit and cadence sequences), and *TFIDF* (pairwise TF-IDF vector Cosine similarity between all tunes). A large-scale experiment has been carried out comparing the performance of these methods in a tune family identification task, and the accuracy of all results has been measured quantitatively by comparison with the expert-annotated ground truth data detailed above.

The experiment was structured as follows:

For all 315 tunes in the ground-truth annotated subset of *The Session* corpus, 9 sets of tune similarity results were generated using all variations of the three core similarity methods, *motif*, *incipit and cadence*, and *TFIDF*, listed below. The overall experimental workflow is illustrated in 2.8. Each results set took the form of a ranked list of similarity between the candidate tune and all other tunes in the corpus. 2.9 illustrates an excerpt from an example results table. The entire experimental workflow was repeated twice for each of the 315 ground-truth annotated tunes, on note- and accent-level input data.

Each results set was compared against ground truth, which comprised of a list of verified members of the candidate’s tune family (see Figure 2.3 for an example). True and false positives were automatically detected and automatically annotated in the similarity results based on this ground truth annotation– for example, please see the ‘family member’ column of Figure 2.9. Based on this annotation, it was possible to calculate mean

Average Precision (mAP) values for each similarity method. These precision values serve as a quantitative indicator of each method’s effectiveness at returning accurate results in specific ranking ranges. They are presented and discussed below in the Results section.

Similarity method and variants:

- *TFIDF*
- *Motif*: Levenshtein distance
- *Motif*: Levenshtein distance (normalized)
- *Incipit and cadence*: Levenshtein distance
- *Incipit and cadence*: Hamming distance
- *Incipit and cadence*: Custom-weighted Hamming distance
- *Incipit*: Levenshtein distance
- *Incipit*: Hamming distance
- *Incipit*: Custom-weighted Hamming distance

Note: explanatory information on the above methodological variations is provided below.

Figure 2.8: Flow chart illustrating similarity experiment workflow.

2.3.2 Motif similarity

Once a candidate tune has been selected, we select the *n*-value (pattern length) at which we will extract a search term pattern. All work reported here uses *n*=6 at accent-level and *n*=8 at

	title	Cosine similarity	family member
0	LordMcDonalds507	1.0	TRUE
1	LordMcDonalds13430	0.794	TRUE
2	LordMcDonalds13432	0.7603	TRUE
3	LordMcDonalds30618	0.673	TRUE
4	LordMcDonalds23658	0.673	TRUE
5	LordMcDonalds13431	0.583	TRUE
6	LordMcDonalds13433	0.2654	TRUE
7	GlentaunThe485	0.231	FALSE

Figure 2.9: Sample results with annotation of true and false positive results based on tune family membership ground truth. These results are specifically for the *TFIDF* method but the results of all 9 methodological variations are scored as True/False in similar fashion. Note: The tune at index 7 above, *GlentaunThe485*, was automatically assigned a tune family membership value of 'FALSE'. However, its Cosine similarity value is very similar to that of *LordMcDonalds13433* at index 6. This specific result is discussed below in section 2.4.2.

note-level. [TODO: explain why?] The candidate tune is located in the “pattern corpus” TF-IDF table and pattern(s) occurring in the tune which have a maximal TF-IDF value are returned. A maximal TF-IDF value indicates that the pattern(s) are prominent or important within the individual tune, even when weighted by their frequency across the corpus as a whole. This guards against inadvertent selection of frequent but less musically-significant corpus-level ‘stop word’ patterns as search terms. The extracted search term pattern(s) are taken as significant or representative motifs within the tune and are used as inputs for an edit-distance-based local pattern similarity search.

In the case of *LordMcDonalds507*, the example tune featured in the structural Figures above, a single search term pattern was extracted at both note- and accent-levels. The accent-level pattern extracted was **[3 3 5 5 2 3]**, which we will use as an example below.

Global and local sequence alignment measures are well-established industry-standard tools in the field of melodic similarity detection [4, 41, 42]. Levenshtein distance [43] is a edit distance calculation which has previously been applied to the task of determining similarity between sequences derived from traditional tunes [42, 44]. It allows fuzzy searching via custom edit distance penalties for substitutions, insertions and deletions of sequence items. This is useful for Irish material with its preponderance of tune variants, arising from the centrality of oral transmission and melodic variation in historic and contemporary traditional practice [45]. In the *motif* implementation of Levenshtein distance, each insertion, deletion and substitution is assigned a default penalty value of 1. Pairwise Levenshtein distance values are calculated between the search term

pattern(s) and all other patterns which occur at least once in the corpus. A maximum distance threshold of 1 is applied to these results, producing a table of similar patterns within 1 edit of the search term pattern(s). per Figure 2.10.

pattern id	distance	patterns
167681	1	[1 3 3 5 5 2 3]
185832	1	[1 3 5 5 2 3]
553454	1	[2 3 3 5 5 2 3]
564365	1	[2 3 5 5 2 3]
768722	1	[3 1 3 5 5 2 3]
786582	1	[3 1 5 5 2 3]
832743	1	[3 2 3 5 5 2 3]
846098	1	[3 2 5 5 2 3]
866329	1	[3 3 1 5 2 3]
875214	1	[3 3 2 5 2 3]

Figure 2.10: Excerpt from similar patterns results as detected via Levenshtein distance for the accent-level search term [3 3 5 5 2 3]. extracted from *LordMcDonalds507*.

Occurrences of these similar patterns are counted for every tune in the corpus, and a list of tunes is returned, ranked in descending order by the number of similar patterns per tune, as illustrated in Figure 2.11.

These counts are taken as a tune similarity metric and are returned in raw and normalized versions. In the normalized results, the total number of similar patterns is divided by the total number of notes in the tune (at note-level) or the total number of accented notes in the tune (at accent-level).

2.3.3 *Incipit and cadence similarity*

The use of incipit search as a finding aid has been fundamental to the history of corpus-based musicology since the pre-computational era [16, 19]. We augment this established approach with inclusion of the first part-ending cadence in addition to the incipit. This decision is informed by previous work on melody and structure in Western folk music as outlined in the Background section. Please see Figure 2.2 for illustration, wherein the incipit and part-ending cadence are highlighted in red on the score.

Rather than making use of the “pattern corpus”, the *incipit and cadence* similarity method first extracts the structurally-important incipit and cadence patterns directly from the feature sequence data for all tunes in the corpus. This data is stored in a table per Figure 2.7 above. Accurate extraction of incipit and cadence patterns is made possible by the high degree of structural

	title	count	family member
1	LordMcDonalds13432	20	TRUE
2	LordMcDonalds23658	20	TRUE
3	LordMcDonalds13430	20	TRUE
4	LordMcDonalds507	20	TRUE
5	LordMcDonalds30618	20	TRUE
6	LordMcDonalds13431	14	TRUE
7	AnDroDesPetitsBateaux27002	12	FALSE
8	HeresToTheMaidenOfBashfulFifteen26348	12	FALSE
9	BillyInTheLowground38167	12	FALSE
10	MapleSugar39281	12	FALSE

Figure 2.11: Top 10 similar tunes as detected via the *motif* method for *LordMcDonalds507* at accent-level. The ‘count’ column contains the number of similar patterns detected per tune.
 NOTE: These are raw rather than normalised *motif* results, as described above.

uniformity which characterises Irish traditional tunes, as illustrated in 2.2 and discussed in the Background section: by targeting bars 1-4 and bars 7-8 we can be confident of extracting the appropriate structurally-important material from all tunes in the corpus.

The *incipit and cadence* method is run on both note- and accent-level input data using two modes: ‘incipit and cadence’ in which the incipit and cadence patterns for each tune are combined, and ‘incipit’ which omits the cadence. This allows us to evaluate whether or not inclusion of the theoretically-important part-ending cadence has a demonstrable effect on similarity results.

When incipits (or incipits and cadences) have been extracted from all tunes, a candidate tune is selected and pairwise edit distances are calculated between its incipit vs those of all other tunes in the corpus. Levenshtein distance is used alongside two variants of Hamming distance: one with default weights, and another with custom weights based on musical consonance/dissonance of substitutions.

Hamming distance [46] is a simpler alternative to Levenshtein distance in which substitutions are permitted but not insertions or deletions (i.e.: both sequences under comparison must be the same length). The experimental work uses a standard Hamming distance implementation, where each substitution required to align two two sequences is scored with the default penalty value of 1.

The third distance metric implements Hamming distance with a custom diatonic substitution penalty matrix, as illustrated in Figure 13. This matrix replaces the default substitution penalty value of 1 with a square matrix in which musically consonant substitutions are penalised less severely than musically dissonant substitutions. This follows a similar approach taken in [4]. In

the substitution matrix, consonant substitutions of the tonic (diatonic scale degree 1), members of the root triad (diatonic scale degrees 1, 3, 5), and the subdominant (scale degree 4) are penalised less severely than other, more dissonant, substitutions.

All variants of the incipit and cadence similarity search return pairwise edit distances between the incipit (or incipit and cadence) of the candidate tune and all other tunes in the corpus, ranked in ascending order— see Figure 2.13 for sample results.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	0	2	0.5	0.5	0.5	2	2
2	2	0	1	0.5	0.5	1	1
3	0.5	2	0	0.5	0.5	2	2
4	0.5	2	2	0	0.5	1	2
5	0.5	2	1	0.5	0	2	1
6	0.5	1	1	0.5	0.5	0	2
7	2	1	2	0.5	0.5	2	0

Figure 2.12: Custom diatonic substitution penalty matrix, as implemented in the *Incipit and cadence: Custom-weighted Hamming distance* similarity method.

2.3.4 TFIDF similarity

The third similarity method, which we call *TFIDF*, takes an entire TFIDF "pattern corpus" table at either note- or accent-level as its input, as illustrated above in Figure 2.6.

Taking a classical Information Retrieval (IR) approach, Cosine similarity values are calculated between the TFIDF vectors for all tunes (i.e.: between all columns in the "pattern corpus" table) and the results are stored in a triangular matrix. Our implementation utilizes the *scikit-learn* [47] Python library's highly-optimised feature extraction toolkit [48], facilitating high-performance local computation of pairwise similarity results for large corpora such as *The Session*. This method was added to provide an industry-standard IR benchmark against which the musicologically-driven *incipit and cadence* and *motif* approaches could be compared.

Once the matrix has been generated, given the title of a candidate tune, a lookup is performed and the pairwise Cosine similarity results between the candidate and all other tunes in the corpus are read from the matrix and ranked in descending order, per the sample results table in Figure 2.9. As per all other methods described above, *TFIDF* similarity is calculated at both note- and accent-level input data.

	title	distance	family member
1	LordMcDonalds507	0.0	TRUE
2	LordMcDonalds13430	2.0	TRUE
3	LordMacDonald17634	3.0	FALSE
4	Wolfes37973	5.0	FALSE
5	Wolfes37976	5.0	FALSE
6	LordMcDonalds13433	5.5	TRUE
7	GanAinm29616	5.5	FALSE
8	LordMcDonalds13432	6.0	TRUE
9	FoxhuntersThe13438	7.0	FALSE
10	AnUglyCustomer17602	7.0	FALSE

Figure 2.13: Sample accent-level *Incipit and cadence: Custom-weighted Hamming distance* results for *LordMcDonalds507*. Note: despite its title, *LordMcDonalds17634* is assigned a value of FALSE in the 'family member' column. This is due to its exclusion from the ground-truth tune family data in the final expert-validation step discussed above in section 2.2.2

2.4 Results

Similarity results tables such as those in the Figures throughout the Methodology section were calculated for all 315 tunes in the ground-truth annotated test subset of *The Session* using each of the nine methodological variations at both note- and accent-level.

Using the ground truth annotation, the 'family member' columns were assigned Boolean values: True if a similarity results was a member of the candidate's tune family, False if not. Based on this flagging of true and false positives, precision values at 1, 5 and 10 were calculated for all results tables. Based on these tune-level precision values, corpus-level mean Average Precision (mAP) at 1, 5 and 10 was calculated for each of the nine similarity methods at note- and accent-level. These high-level precision results and are presented in the summary figures and tables below.

mAP@1 measures the average effectiveness of a given metric at returning a true positive as the top ranked similarity search result. mAP@5 and 10 measure the proportion of true positives respectively in the top 5 and top 10 tune similarity search results. The use of a ranking metric rather than a binary classification reflects the ultimate use case of a musicologist in need of accurate first-page search results. mAP gives a balanced indication of overall performance in a single metric, rather than aggregating evaluations of the best and worst results, giving many of the same benefits of Discounted Cumulative Gain (DCG). A similar approach to quantitative analysis of folk music similarity results via mAP at 1 and 3 was used in [6]. The mAP values below represent the precision of each metric when applied to the task of identifying tune family

membership within the ground-truth annotated test subset of *The Session*.

Mean average precision for The Session corpus:
Comparing all FONN similarity metrics on duration-weighted note-level input data.

Figure 2.14: Visualization of note-level mean Average Precision results for all 9 similarity method variations.

2.4.1 Discussion

From the note-level results presented in Figures 2.14 and 2.16, it is evident that the *TFIDF* method and all variants of the *incipit and cadence* method were highly effective at returning a true positive result at ranking 1, as indicated by their mAP@1 values. All *incipit and cadence* variations retained relatively high precision at rankings 5 and 10, as measured by mAP@5 and mAP@10, while *TFIDF* exhibited a steeper decline in accuracy.

Figure 2.15: Visualization of accent-level mean Average Precision results for all 9 similarity method variations.

Of the variations on the *incipit and cadence* method, Levenshtein distance applied to the combined incipit and cadence sequences had the highest precision at all three rankings (*Incipit and cadence – Levenshtein distance* in the figures above). Overall the *incipit and cadence* methods outperformed their *incipit* variations, but only by a narrow margin.

The *motif* methods were generally less effective overall, with the *motif – Levenshtein distance (normalized)* method yielding the least accurate results at note-level.

From Figures 2.15 and 2.17, it is clear that most similarity methods exhibited reduced precision

Metric	mAP @ 1	mAP @ 5	mAP @ 10
TFIDF	1.00	0.49	0.30
Incipit & cadence -- Custom weighted Hamming distance	0.99	0.58	0.39
Incipit & cadence -- Hamming distance	0.99	0.63	0.44
Incipit & cadence -- Levenshtein distance	0.99	0.65	0.46
Incipit -- Custom weighted Hamming distance	0.98	0.58	0.38
Incipit -- Hamming distance	0.99	0.62	0.42
Incipit -- Levenshtein distance	0.99	0.63	0.44
Motif -- Levenshtein distance	0.70	0.29	0.18
Motif -- Levenshtein distance (normalized)	0.61	0.28	0.17

Figure 2.16: Table of note-level mean Average Precision results for all 9 similarity method variations.

Metric	mAP @ 1	mAP @ 5	mAP @ 10
TFIDF	1.00	0.65	0.46
Incipit & cadence -- Custom weighted Hamming distance	0.42	0.15	0.08
Incipit & cadence -- Hamming distance	0.43	0.17	0.10
Incipit & cadence -- Levenshtein distance	0.49	0.19	0.10
Incipit -- Custom weighted Hamming distance	0.25	0.12	0.07
Incipit -- Hamming distance	0.26	0.12	0.08
Incipit -- Levenshtein distance	0.25	0.14	0.09
Motif -- Levenshtein distance	0.38	0.25	0.17
Motif -- Levenshtein distance (normalized)	0.46	0.29	0.19

Figure 2.17: Table of accent-level mean Average Precision results for all 9 similarity method variations.

when applied to accent-level input data. The *incipit* variations of the *incipit and cadence* method show the greatest decrease in precision between note- and accent-level. Though overall precision is lower at accent-level, inclusion of the cadence appears to boost performance. The *TFIDF* method is an exception to the trend: it is the only similarity method to exhibit increased precision at accent-level.

Taking all methodological variations into account at both levels, the best-performing approaches

as measured by mean Average Precision are *TFIDF* at accent-level and *Incipit and cadence – Levenshtein distance* at note-level, which exhibit almost identical precision results.

2.4.2 Analysis

Looking at the sample *TFIDF* results table in Figure 2.9, all of the top eight similarity results are verified members of the Lord McDonald's tune family with one exception, *GlentaunThe485*. On qualitative inspection by a domain expert, this tune was found to be melodically related to the Lord McDonald's family, although missing from the family membership documented in the ethnomusicological literature.

Future work will involve comprehensive re-annotation of tune family ground truth based on such domain expert inspection of similarity results. This process will aid the discovery of new knowledge in the field of ethnomusicology, expanding, verifying and quantifying tune family membership data. It will also provide more accurate and comprehensive ground truth for development and refinement of new iterations of these tools.

Taking accent-level *TFIDF* as a relatively performant benchmark, it is illustrative to compare against other similarity methods in more detail. Firstly, comparing against note-level *TFIDF* results: why are the note-level mAP values significantly lower? This may be explained by the ethnomusicological theory of the importance of accent- rather than note-level melodic patterns in defining the unique melodic signatures of traditional Irish tunes, but further testing is required before a definitive conclusion can be drawn.

The performance of the various *incipit and cadence* approaches may seem to contradict this tentative conclusion, as the precision values for all *incipit and cadence* methods are higher at note- rather than accent-level. However, the incipit and cadence sequences are significantly longer at note-level than at accent-level. For example, for *LordMcDonalds507* they are:

Accent-level: [5 5 4 2 5 5 3 3 1 5 3]

Note-level: [5 1 3 1 5 1 3 1 4 3 4 2 1 6 1 5 1 3 1 5 1 3 1 5 6 5 4 3 1 1 3 4 3 2 1 2 1 6 5 6 1 2 3 1 1]

Sample results based on the above sequences from *LordMcDonalds507* can be seen in Figure 2.18. Results based on the longer note-level sequence clearly outperform those based on the shorter accent-level sequence. In addition, the note-level 'distance' column values are higher and more finely gradated than their accent-level equivalents.

This suggests that accent-level incipit and cadence patterns may be too short to provide enough graduation in the results ranking to effectively distinguish true positive results from false positives. This issue of pattern length may also be a factor in the relatively poor precision of the *motif* results, as discussed below.

In general, at both note- and accent-level, the *motif* results exhibit lower precision results than either *incipit and cadence* or *TFIDF*. It appears that two major factors are largely to blame for their relatively poor performance:

	title	distance	family member
1	LordMcDonalds507	0	TRUE
2	DecisionThe23894	0	FALSE
3	RoxburghCastle34558	0	FALSE
4	MickFlahertys37730	0	FALSE
5	Vidarvalsen21493	0	FALSE
6	FlowerOfKristiansandThe29215	0	FALSE
7	Vidarvalsen20538	0	FALSE
8	Jacksons20513	1	FALSE
9	Lynchs16566	1	FALSE
10	SandysNewChanter36918	1	FALSE

	title	distance	family member
1	LordMcDonalds507	0	TRUE
2	LordMcDonalds13430	3	TRUE
3	LordMacDonald17634	8	FALSE
4	LordMcDonalds13433	11	TRUE
5	GlentaunThe485	12	FALSE
6	LordMcDonalds13432	15	TRUE
7	LordMcDonalds13431	15	TRUE
8	LordMcDonalds23658	16	TRUE
9	LordMcDonalds30618	16	TRUE
10	GlentaunThe31799	16	FALSE

Figure 2.18: Top 10 accent- and note-level results for *LordMcDonalds507* using Incipit and cadence – Levenshtein distance method.

Firstly, the current method depends on extraction of representative search term pattern(s) via maximal TF-IDF ranking as a first and fundamental step. This approach ensures the extracted search term patterns are locally prominent/frequent within the candidate tune, but it cannot rank or differentiate patterns based on melodic or structural significance. If the search term pattern extracted for a given tune is frequent but musically insignificant there is a high likelihood that the subsequent similarity calculations will return inaccurate results.

To take *LordMcDonalds507* again as an example, and to recap: Figure 2.10 displays an excerpt from the table of similar patterns detected via Levenshtein distance at accent-level, all of which require only one edit to align with the search term pattern, [3 3 5 5 2 3]. Occurrences of these similar patterns were counted across all tunes in the corpus; the tunes were ranked in descending order of their similar pattern counts, which gave the highly accurate *motif* similarity results displayed in Figure 2.11.

For *LordMcDonalds507*, the accent-level *motif* results are more accurate than their note-level equivalents, despite corpus-wide precision values indicating that note-level *motif* similarity outperforms accent-level on average across the full set of experimental results (Figures 2.14, 2.16, 2.15, 2.17).

On the annotated score in Figure 2.19, we can see all occurrences of the search term pattern [3 3 5 5 2 3] highlighted in red in *LordMcDonalds507*. This pattern overlaps in part with the structurally-important first part-ending cadence and occurs four times in total but contains no material from the incipit. Despite its frequency, the pattern almost entirely falls outside the academically-identified structurally significant sub-sequences within the tune. Although it still returns accurate results, to maximise results accuracy in general, search term patterns should align more closely and more dependably with the incipit and/or first part-ending cadence. Reviewing the approach to search term extraction for motif similarity and experimenting with alternatives to the current maximal TFIDF approach will be a priority in our future work.

Lord McDonald's

Figure 2.19: Score for *LordMcDonalds507*, annotated to show occurrences of the search term pattern **[3 3 5 5 2 3]**

For a contrasting example in which the *motif* method successfully extracts a structurally-significant search term pattern, let us examine the results for candidate tune *RoadToLisdoonvarna249*. This tune is a member of the Road to Lisdoonvarna tune family; it contrasts with *LordMcDonalds507* as it is a much shorter and simpler melody and is a jig (6/8 time signature) rather than a reel (4/4 time signature). The accent-level search term pattern **[1 4 5 2 3 7]** was extracted by maximal TF-IDF: its occurrences in *RoadToLisdoonvarna249* are illustrated in Figure 2.20.

Although less frequent than the search term pattern extracted from Lord McDonald's, this pattern includes 3 of the 4 incipit bars and overlaps with the entire first part-ending cadence. Pattern and tune similarity results based on this search term are presented in Figures 2.21 and 2.22. The

tune similarity results ultimately exhibit a similar high degree of accuracy to those produced for *LordMcDonalds507*, albeit in this example the entire *motif* methodology is working as-intended.

Figure 2.20: Score for *RoadToLisdoonvarna249*, annotated to show occurrences of the search term pattern [1 4 5 2 3 7]

pattern id	distance	patterns
55826	1	[1 1 5 2 3 7]
119535	1	[1 2 5 2 3 7]
180854	1	[1 3 5 2 3 7]
208014	1	[1 4 1 5 2 3 7]
212104	1	[1 4 2 2 3 7]
213515	1	[1 4 2 3 7]
227316	1	[1 4 4 5 2 3 7]
229367	1	[1 4 5 1 2 3 7]
229677	1	[1 4 5 1 3 7]
230569	1	[1 4 5 2 1 3 7]

Figure 2.21: Excerpt from similar patterns results as detected via Levenshtein distance for the accent-level search term [1 4 5 2 3 7]. extracted from *RoadToLisdoonvarna249*.

A second and more complex consideration contributing to the relatively poor performance of the *motif* methods is the interplay between choice of edit distance metric, length of candidate pattern, and the range of pattern lengths for which *n*-gram patterns are extracted. Detailed discussion of these interrelated factors is outside the scope of this document, but one recurring observation is

	title	count	family member
1	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe12965	63	TRUE
2	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe12970	32	TRUE
3	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe249	32	TRUE
4	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe41930	24	TRUE
5	TrimTheVelvet27979	18	FALSE
6	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe32320	16	TRUE
7	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe36691	16	TRUE
8	SeanReids40792	14	FALSE
9	ShaskeenThe13631	12	FALSE
10	RoadToLisdoonvarnaThe36697	12	TRUE

Figure 2.22: Top 10 similar tunes as detected via the *motif* method for *RoadToLisdoonvarna249* at accent-level.

that the longer 8-element note-level search term patterns on average give more accurate results than the 6-element accent-level patterns. Future work will iteratively test and evaluate the performance of custom-weighted Levenshtein and Hamming distance metrics on longer patterns at both note- and accent-level.

2.5 Future work

In addition to the refinements to our current methodology mentioned in the 2.4 section above, we plan to design and run a cross-corpus similarity experiment in spring/summer 2023. Using a subset of the best-performing methods reported above, we plan to measure melodic similarity between The Session (Irish), Neuma (French) and Meertens (Dutch) corpora. This work will involve collaboration with colleagues in Polifonia partner organisations Conservatoire National des Arts et Métiers (CNAM) and Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen (KNAW), which will be aided by a student exchange between University of Galway and CNAM in February-March 2023.

Further work to develop and improve the best-performing *TFIDF* and *incipit and cadence – Levenshtein distance* similarity methods will be a medium-long term priority. To-do items include weighting pattern TF-IDF values by their index/location within tunes; filtering out ‘stop word’ patterns; refining the diatonic substitution matrix (Figure 2.12); and developing an alternative to extraction of search term patterns via maximal TF-IDF ranking.

3 Live Queries in Linked Open Data

3.1 Introduction

The focus of this section of the deliverable is a strand of research in which we present and preserve the extracted patterns in a robust structure for effective music analysis. Ontologies and knowledge graphs (KGs) provide a way to represent, organize, and structure the information and knowledge obtained from the analysis of musical patterns, and thus offer easier access, manipulation, and analysis of the data. Additionally, ontologies and knowledge graphs may provide a shared vocabulary and a standardized way of representing musical information; this will enable us to perform integration of information from different corpora and cross-referencing and linking of related tunes. Further, it offers a platform for exploration of relationships among different types of patterns and tunes.

Therefore, we have developed a pattern ontology and a pipeline for converting our pattern corpus into a KG, taking advantage of the ontology. Ontologies and KGs are used throughout Polifonia for these and related purposes, and thus this work feeds into a larger goal of creating a large inter-linked collection of musical heritage data.

The pattern ontology and KG we will describe are designed to store the types of patterns described and extracted in the previous section (and other types).

The pattern ontology we will describe includes both pattern-related information and metadata. The pattern-related information includes the contents of the pattern, number of occurrences, location in the tune, duration in beats, pattern type (e.g. our patterns are n -grams), length (n -gram value). The pitch class values of the whole tune are also represented. The metadata includes tune name, tune family, tune dance type or form (e.g. reel or jig), tune key signature, tune corpus, and finally tune ABC content for display.

The pipeline we have developed is derived from the pipeline described by [49], and takes advantage of the *JAMS* standard for musical annotations [50] and the *SPARQL Anything* tool described by [51]. The code is available on GitHub.

Although our methods are generic, in this section of the deliverable we again describe their application to an Irish dance music dataset, *The Session*. As described in the previous chapter, the whole dataset has been processed through FoNN to generate patterns. The FoNN tool produces a Python Pickle file. It becomes the input to our JAMS Pipeline, which creates a JAMS file for each tune. A total of 40,152 JAMS files have been created, which were processed to create the KG. A total of around 45 million (44,979,281) statements were generated and deployed using Blazegraph¹. Later, this model was evaluated based on competency questions, described later.

¹<https://blazegraph.com/>

The evaluation suggests that the proposed model successfully addresses most of the requirements of musicologists who might wish to use the KG for analysis. The KG can be accessed through the Polifonia server (<https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/fonn/sparql>).

3.2 Methods

The Pattern2KG-JAMS pipeline workflow is shown in Figure 3.1 and can be summarised as follows. Feature sequences (n -grams of pitch-class values) are extracted through the FoNN tool, as described in the previous chapter. They are stored in a Pandas DataFrame and become the input to the pipeline. In the next stage, these sequences are converted to JAMS annotations. For each tune, a file of JAMS annotations is created. Afterward, these JAMS files are processed with the help of the pattern ontology and SPARQL Anything engine [51] to generate a KG in the form of `rdf`. These steps are described in more detail in the following sections.

Figure 3.1: Abstract workflow of the proposed system

3.2.1 Pattern Ontology – Music Annotation Framework

The purpose of the Musical Annotation Pattern (MAP) proposed by [49] as part of Polifonia research is to model different types of musical annotation such as chords, structure, and patterns. The MAP is based on the JAMS annotation standard [52]. Briefly, JAMS is a standard format

for musical annotations. It was originally intended for annotations of audio recordings, but can be used for annotations of score data also. JAMS defines a JSON schema in which annotations can be stored, with fields such as `artist` and `title`, and a *list of annotations*, where each annotation includes a `time`, `duration`, and `value`. Such a structure can store, for example, the chord sequence for a song by storing each chord's name as the `value`, together with the start time and duration of that chord observation.

Since MAP uses JAMS, MAP class names start with the name `jams`. The ontology is shown in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: Pattern Ontology based on Music Ontology Pattern

Two main classes are defined as `jams:JAMSScoreAnnotation` and `jams:JAMSAnnotation`. The `jams:JAMSAnnotation` class records multiple `jams:JAMSObservations`. At the bottom of the image, enclosed in the rectangle are the specific classes that deal with pattern annotations. Of them, the first class is the `jams:ScorePatternOccurrence` class which expresses the pitch class patterns. Its properties, such as `jams:hasLocation` and `jams:hasPatternType` are defined to represent the location of a pattern and type respectively. The actual content (i.e., pitch class values) is described as a separate class, i.e., `jams:Pattern` and it is linked with `jams:ScorePatternOccurrence` by `jams:ofPattern` property. This is later used to connect a pattern to a tune, and indirectly to connect tunes to each other via patterns (in the same or different corpora).

3.2.2 JAMS Pattern Schema

JAMS offers a predefined schema for storing musical patterns². However, this "JKU pattern" includes only a pattern ID field, and does not include pattern contents. Therefore, we need to create an extension. JAMS offers the possibility to create custom local schemas to store user-defined data. So, a local schema was designed to store JAMS annotations of FoNN-derived patterns. The developed FoNN-pattern schema is shown on the left side of Figure 3.3. Afterward, through custom Python scripts, pitch class sequences in the form of dataframe were converted to .jams files. The instance of a .jams file is shown on the right side of figure 3.3. For simplicity purposes, we have shown a file containing a single pattern. Further, the tune file details are shown in the `file_metadata` section.

Figure 3.3: Left: FoNN-Pattern schema for JAMS and Right: Sample JAMS annotation file for a tune

In this research, we processed The Session dataset and thus the created .jams file for each of its tunes. In the `file_metadata` section the identifiers link to a URL on The Session’s website. In the next stage, each .jams file was converted into a Knowledge Graph file, as detailed in the next section.

²<https://jams.readthedocs.io/en/stable/namespaces/pattern.html#patternjku>

3.2.3 Knowledge Graph – RDF generation using SPARQL Anything

Figure 3.4 shows a snippet of the KG developed based on the above described ontology. The unique URI for representing jams:JAMSAnnotation is hashed with SHA1 to ensure interoperability among the other Polifonia Ontology Network Knowledge graph.

Figure 3.4: A snippet of an RDF of two tunes representing the connection based on Patterns

The `jams:Pattern` is represented by a URI. This URI links various tunes when the same pattern is found there in some other tune. In Figure 3.4 the links between the tunes are shown with the help of a dotted line. It shows how patterns of the same content are linked together to create an aggregated view of the whole knowledge graph. It is also worth mentioning that a tune can belong to any corpus and thus tunes of different corpora can be conveniently linked together, and thus it offers an opportunity to perform inter-corpus pattern analysis. Multiple corpora can be created at different times by different authors, and combined seamlessly. Furthermore, it is scalable in the sense that further corpora can be automatically added to enrich the knowledge graph without making any changes to the existing model.

3.3 Evaluation: Queries and Results

A common method for the evaluation of ontologies is to develop the requirements in the form of competency questions. Later the questions are translated to SPARQL queries for extracting the modeled knowledge to ensure the retrieved result serves the purpose. The competency questions play a frame of reference role for evaluating ontologies [53]. The competency questions are intended to explore the scope of the domain modelling. Therefore, competency questions should be developed with the domain experts.

Through re-use of existing Polifonia competency questions and refinement for our purposes, we finalized the requirements (listed in 3.1). In summary, these questions mainly cover tunes, tune similarities, patterns, and relationship aspects.

Table 3.1: List of competency questions

No	Question
CQ1	Pattern searching: Given a pattern, retrieve a list of the tunes where it was found.
CQ2	Similar Tunes: How can we get a (ranked) list of similar tunes (based on patterns) for a given input tune?
CQ3	Can we identify what types of patterns are present in the Knowledge graph? For example, a set of notes, accented notes, or pitch-class-values, etc.
CQ4	Retrieve the list of patterns and their frequency of occurrence per tune.
CQ5	Can we find patterns that play a bridging role between musical traditions/datasets?
CQ6	Where does a pattern appear in a tune? For instance, it could be found at the beginning, middle, or end of a tune.
CQ7	Given a tune family find what patterns are characteristic of the family.
CQ8	Given a national corpus, what patterns are characteristic of that corpus?
CQ9	How can we find metadata-related information about a tune/-corpus?
CQ10	Similar Tunes: Starting with two patterns, find a list of tunes that both occur in. Co-occurrence of patterns: Given a pattern, find list of patterns that co-occur with it and the tunes that they co-occur in.

For each competency question, a SPARQL query was developed. Below, we present a few SPARQL queries and their results.

Patterns base tune retrieval: Given a pattern, retrieve a list of the tunes where it was found. In this case, a user wants to find a list of tunes where a pattern is found, therefore, in the query shown below, variable `?Pattern` is assigned to the given pattern and in the following statements, its occurrence is ensured with `jams:ofPattern` predicate. Finally, using the ontology information further relevant statements are added to reach the tune name. The results of this query are shown in Figure 3.7.

```

PREFIX jams: <http://w3id.org/polifonia/ontology/jams/>
PREFIX mc: <http://w3id.org/polifonia/ontology/musical-composition/>

SELECT distinct ?tuneName ?tuneType
WHERE
{
VALUES ?Pattern
{<http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/2_4_7_5>}
?observation jams:ofPattern ?pattern.
?tuneFile jams:includesObservation ?observation.
?tuneFile jams:isJAMSAnnotationOf ?musicalComposition.
?musicalComposition mc:title ?tuneName.
} limit 100
    
```

Listing 3.1: Pattern searching: A query to find the tunes that a given pattern occur in.

Pattern	TuneWhereThisPatternOccur
1 http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/2_4_7_5	A Morning Tune
2 http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/2_4_7_5	A Mother's Love Is A Blessing
3 http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/2_4_7_5	Aileen Bonner's
4 http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/2_4_7_5	A Munster
5 http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/2_4_7_5	A Morning In Summer
6 http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/2_4_7_5	100WattReels24291
7 http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/2_4_7_5	186838861
8 http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/2_4_7_5	A Whisky Kiss
9 http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/2_4_7_5	Aileen's
10 http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/2_4_7_5	A Winston
11 http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/2_4_7_5	Aileen's Slow
12 http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/2_4_7_5	Aine's Invitation

Figure 3.5: Results of tunes where a given pattern was found.

Patterns across corpus:- Given a national corpus, what patterns are characteristic of that corpus?

This question means that the user is interested in finding the most frequent patterns in a given dataset (which may aligned to some national tradition). A query is shown below. The results are shown in Figure 3.6.

```

PREFIX jams:<http://w3id.org/polifonia/ontology/jams/>
PREFIX mc: <http://w3id.org/polifonia/ontology/musical-composition/>
PREFIX prov: <http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#>

SELECT ?pattern (count(?pattern) as ?countFreq)
WHERE
{
?observation jams:ofPattern ?pattern.
?tuneFile jams:includesObservation ?observation.
?tuneFile jams:isJAMSAnnotationOf ?musicalComposition.
?musicalComposition mc:title ?tuneName.
?musicalComposition jams:tuneType ?tuneFamily.
?musicalComposition prov:wasDerivedFrom ?jamsFile.
?jamsFile prov:wasDerivedFrom "The_Session".
}
group by ?pattern
order by desc (?countFreq)
limit 100
    
```

Listing 3.2: A query to find the most common pattern(s) in the corpus query

Patterns in a given tune: Here a user is interested in finding the most common patterns in a given tune. A suitable query is shown below, and the results are shown in Figure 3.7.

```

PREFIX jams:<http://w3id.org/polifonia/ontology/jams/>
PREFIX mc: <http://w3id.org/polifonia/ontology/musical-composition/>

SELECT ?tune_name ?pattern (count(?pattern) as ?patternFreq)
{
?tune_file mc:title ?tune_name.
FILTER (?tune_name = "Bowe's_Favourite_").
?xx jams:isJAMSAnnotationOf ?tune_file.
?xx jams:includesObservation ?observation .
?observation jams:ofPattern ?pattern .
} group by ?tune_name ?pattern
order by DESC (?patternFreq )
    
```

Listing 3.3: A query to find the most common pattern in a given tune query

	pattern	countFreq
1	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/1_1_1_1	"5579" ^{^xsd:integer}
2	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/5_5_5_5	"3886" ^{^xsd:integer}
3	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/1_5_1_5	"3815" ^{^xsd:integer}
4	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/1_1_5_1	"3617" ^{^xsd:integer}
5	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/5_1_5_1	"3535" ^{^xsd:integer}
6	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/3_2_1_1	"3455" ^{^xsd:integer}
7	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/2_1_1_1	"3441" ^{^xsd:integer}
8	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/1_1_5_5	"3332" ^{^xsd:integer}
9	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/1_1_1_5	"3234" ^{^xsd:integer}
10	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/1_5_5_5	"3191" ^{^xsd:integer}
11	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/1_1_3_1	"3139" ^{^xsd:integer}
12	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/5_1_1_1	"3086" ^{^xsd:integer}

Figure 3.6: Common patterns in the corpus. This includes some trivial or uninteresting patterns which nevertheless occur frequently. They can also be removed by later filtering.

	tune_name	pattern	patternFreq
1	Bowe's Favourite	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/1_2_5_1	"4" ^{^xsd:integer}
2	Bowe's Favourite	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/2_5_1_3	"4" ^{^xsd:integer}
3	Bowe's Favourite	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/3_1_2_3_1	"4" ^{^xsd:integer}
4	Bowe's Favourite	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/3_1_2_3	"4" ^{^xsd:integer}
5	Bowe's Favourite	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/5_1_3_1	"4" ^{^xsd:integer}
6	Bowe's Favourite	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/1_2_3_1	"4" ^{^xsd:integer}
7	Bowe's Favourite	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/1_2_5_1_3	"4" ^{^xsd:integer}
8	Bowe's Favourite	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/4_2_3_4_6	"4" ^{^xsd:integer}
9	Bowe's Favourite	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/2_3_4_6	"4" ^{^xsd:integer}
10	Bowe's Favourite	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/6_2_4_2	"4" ^{^xsd:integer}
11	Bowe's Favourite	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/4_2_3_4	"4" ^{^xsd:integer}
12	Bowe's Favourite	http://w3id.org/polifonia/resource/pattern/6_4_6_4	"3" ^{^xsd:integer}

Figure 3.7: Common patterns in the given tune

3.4 Conclusion

In this chapter we have presented an ontology and KG design for musical patterns, and a pipeline for processing raw pattern data to KG via a software pipeline which uses Python code, the Music Annotation Pattern, JAMS annotations, the Pattern Ontology and SPARQL Anything. We have shown some simple examples of the resulting KG answering competency questions.

4 Compliance to the FAIR principles

This section encompasses information relevant to knowledge management in the project and to making Polifonia FAIR (operating according to principles of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).

This deliverable is a research report on patterns, including different methods to extract patterns from different types of data sources (RDF and non-RDF format). While those methods will be further used to produce components for the Polifonia Ecosystem, this deliverable itself does not contain a component of the Polifonia Ecosystem. Nevertheless, producing this deliverable (D3.4) we observed the 'Polifonia 10 Rules for Open Science'.¹

The coming deliverable D3.5 will contain the corresponding Polifonia Ecosystem components, including GitHub and Zenodo releases where relevant. The following items will be delivered, including their compliance to the FAIR principles, as part of D3.5.

The Session Type: External Data hosted on <https://thesession.org/>. Will not be re-hosted by Polifonia. For reproducibility, our derived numerical results can be reproduced by downloading The Session data and using the software below.

FONN-tools Type: software, with accompanying Documentation. Previous version is in GitHub https://github.com/polifonia-project/folk_ngram_analysis and Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/record/5768216#.YbEAbS2Q3T8>. Updated version will be released and deposited in Zenodo with updated metadata.

Knowledge Graph creation pipeline Type: Software, with accompanying Documentation. Will be added to GitHub and deposited in Zenodo with appropriate metadata and license.

Pattern Knowledge Graph and Ontology, and accompanying SPARQL queries Type: KG and Ontology. Aligned to PON. Will be added to GitHub and deposited in Zenodo with appropriate metadata and license.

¹Described in the Polifonia Data Management Plan, 2nd version.

5 Conclusions

This deliverable has reported on a complete system for identifying and processing patterns, using them to answer research questions, and making them available as linked open data. The system is generic, but has been demonstrated here on an Irish folk dataset.

Several strands of research are ongoing and planned for forthcoming deliverables:

- Cross-corpus pattern analysis – already enabled by our methods.
- New types of patterns, including:
 - Polyphonic patterns.
 - Ornamentation patterns.
 - Structural patterns.
- Refinements to pattern similarity methods, such as pattern filtering and note substitution weightings.
- New research results, such as identifying previously unidentified tune family members, based on successful performance in ground-truth tune families.
- Use of patterns for classification (D3.6).
- Publication of current software tools as Polifonia ecosystem components (D3.5).

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